

in Thanjavur delta were done at 10-day intervals. Ten varieties were planted each year except 1977-78, when only 8 were planted. No crop protection was provided.

Varieties evaluated were:

1975-76: AD11585, ADT31, IET1722, IR20, IR26, TKM8, Pusa 33-18, Tainan 3(M), Bhavani, Ponni.
 1976-77: AD54-1, AD5620, AD6380, AS3821, ADT31, CRM10-5747, IET2881, IR20, Pusa 4-1-11-1, Bhavani.
 1977-78: AD9186, ADT31, IET1722, IR20, IR26, TM1251, Tiruveni, Vaigai.
 1978-79: AD5231, AD6120, AD6970, AD7211, AD7481, AD13893, ADT32, AS3704, IR26, IR34.
 1979-80: AD6120, AD4481, AD8991, ADT31, ADT32, ADT33, AS3704, IR34, PL29, TKM9.

The average disease incidence was recorded at the ninth stage of crop growth using the standard evaluation system. Higher incidence of BS and NBLs was observed in late plantings (see table). The diseases appear to cause significant yield reductions only in the second season crop. ■

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Seasonal incidence of brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot in Thanjavur, India.

Date of planting	Disease incidence (%)					
	1975-76	1976-77	1977-78	1978-79	1979-80	Mean
	<i>Brown spot</i>					
15/6	—	17.2	4.8	—	7.4	5.9
25/6	—	13.4	11.6	—	5.8	6.2
5/7	—	13.2	7.9	6.9	9.4	7.4
15/7	15.0	18.1	14.0	10.4	6.3	12.8
25/7	18.9	17.3	12.4	9.7	14.8	14.6
5/8	14.0	14.2	13.7	12.2	19.2	14.7
15/8	9.7	11.0	16.4	15.2	18.5	14.2
25/8	7.2	14.6	8.4	7.9	14.0	10.4
5/9	5.1	14.4	11.2	6.4	20.3	11.5
15/9	8.4	17.5	9.5	14.2	12.2	12.4
25/9	7.9	16.8	14.4	17.1	11.0	13.4
5/10	12.2	21.2	19.3	19.9	9.9	16.5
15/10	17.5	26.5	15.5	16.4	18.2	18.8
25/10	26.4	26.9	31.4	19.7	37.4	28.4
5/11	31.9	25.7	46.4	29.4	35.2	33.7
15/11	35.5	37.1	53.1	37.0	42.6	41.1
25/11	47.7	42.0	67.4	51.4	43.1	50.3
5/12	46.8	50.3	59.5	48.1	53.3	51.6
15/12	53.1	68.7	66.1	47.4	55.2	58.1
25/12	51.6	62.4	64.2	48.0	50.0	55.2
	<i>Narrow brown leaf spot</i>					
15/6	6.3	—	15.1	—	12.6	6.8
25/6	8.7	—	15.5	5.6	7.4	7.4
5/7	—	—	—	10.5	9.5	3.9
15/7	—	—	12.7	—	—	2.5
25/7	—	—	13.2	3.6	—	3.4
5/8	5.0	—	13.7	9.4	—	5.6
15/8	7.3	7.3	7.2	14.5	—	7.3
25/8	5.4	9.6	—	7.8	—	4.6
5/9	—	17.2	—	10.2	—	5.5
15/9	—	10.1	9.5	—	—	3.9
25/9	10.4	—	11.6	4.6	—	5.3
5/10	9.9	—	14.6	7.9	3.5	7.2
15/10	8.9	—	15.6	—	9.6	6.8
25/10	10.0	7.5	14.6	—	—	6.4
5/11	10.9	13.6	13.4	15.2	—	10.6
15/11	15.4	19.1	12.9	17.6	14.7	15.9
25/11	29.9	20.6	18.5	19.7	20.3	21.8
5/12	31.7	47.2	29.7	37.3	32.5	39.7
15/12	32.2	43.0	26.8	26.2	29.3	31.5
25/12	28.5	36.5	27.5	24.4	22.0	27.8

Pest management and control INSECTS

Major insect pests of paddy in Guyana

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A double-cropping system of rice cultivation is recommended in Guyana, although continuous cropping is practiced extensively. The autumn crop (May-Jun) accounts for 90,000-110,000 ha and the spring crop (Dec-Jan) for 40,000-50,000 ha. The rice belt spans

most of the Atlantic coastal lands from Crabwood Creek in the east to the Pomeroon in the west, including Berbice, Demerara, and Essequibo counties. Farmholdings range from less than 1 ha to more than 500 ha.

Rice, the staple cereal, also is an invaluable foreign exchange earner and provides more than 50,000 jobs. Land preparation and harvesting are completely mechanized. Pregerminated seeds are broadcast under wet cultivation method and fertilizers and pesticides are applied manually except in large hold-

ings where applications are by air.

Pest problems have increased with a change from dry to wet cultivation, introduction of double or continuous cropping, increase in hectareage, and development of pesticide resistance. The cultivars used have no genes for insect and disease resistance. The table shows the major insect pests of wetland rice in Guyana and their occurrence in relation to growth stages. Two storage pests have been included because recent studies show significant field infestation and damage. ■

Major insect pests of wetland rice in Guyana, South America.

Growth stage	Pest		Damage
	Scientific name	Common name	
Emergence to maximum tillering	1. <i>Helodytes foveolatus</i> Duval (Curculionidae: Coleoptera)	Rice water weevil	Larva feeds on roots. Adult feeds on eye of pre-germinated seeds.
	2. <i>Hydrellia deonieri</i> Rambajan (Ephydriidae: Diptera)	Rice leafminer Rice blackfly	Larva feeds in growing shoot, causes deadheart.
	3. <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (Smith) (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Fall armyworm	Larva feeds on seedling leaves, causes burnt tip, later defoliation.
	4. <i>Mocis punctularis</i> Hubner (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Rice looper	
	5. <i>Neoconocephalus</i> Spp. <i>Caulopsis</i> Spp. (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves that appear shredded, cobweb.
Panicle initiation to heading	1. <i>Caulopsis cupsidata</i> Scudder (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves and ball, causes whitehead.
Heading to hard dough	1. <i>Oebalus poecilus</i> Dallas (Pentatomidae: Hemiptera)	Stink bug or paddy bug	Nymph and adult feed on grains at milk stage, cause wind paddy or atrophied glumes; at dough stage cause broken barrels, discolored rice after milling.
Hard dough to harvest, storage	1. <i>Sitotroga cerealella</i> (Olivier) (Gelechiidae: Lepidoptera)	Angoumois grain moth	Larva feeds on kernel.
	2. <i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i> (Fabricius) (Bostrichidae: Coleoptera)	Lesser grain borer	

Rice gall midge incidence in the dry season

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Rice gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*), a major insect pest in late-planted fields in the wet season (May-November) in the Andhra Pradesh Krishna and Godavari deltas, has become a major problem in the dry season (November-April) in the Godavari delta since 1978. The percentage silver shoots or galls recorded in

Percent silver shoots in dry season, Maruteru, India.

Trial	Silver shoots (%)			
	1979		1980	
	Mean	Maximum	Mean	Maximum
Uniform Variety Trial 2	11	20	5	8
Uniform Variety Trial 3	17	24	18	25
Uniform Variety Trial 4	16	28	13	8

coordinated variety trials show the high pressure of gall midge at Maruteru center (see table).

It is likely that extensive use of pesticides to control insects has resulted in the destruction of predators and parasites of

rice gall midge. Popular *rabi season* varieties Jaya, Prabhat, Prakash, Rasi, and Tella Hamsa are susceptible to rice gall midge. BPT1235 and IR36 are promising early-maturing, gall midge-resistant varieties. ■

Effects of rice plant age on diopsis oviposition and plant susceptibility

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Diopsis thoracica (West), a serious pest limiting rice yields in West Africa, prefers plants of particular ages for oviposition. Confirmation of the specific age range would be useful in planning pest management programs involving host plant resistance and other control measures.

Pregerminated seeds of 2 rice varieties

Diopsis thoracica eggs laid on rice plants of different ages and subsequent development of dead-hearts in Sierra Leone.^a

DT ^b	IR5			GH106-76		
	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)
10	4 cd	6 b	1.5	2 ab	4 ab	2.0
20	11 ab	13 a	1.2	2 ab	3 b	1.5
30	14 a	14 a	1.0	5 a	6 a	1.2
40	8 bc	6 b	0.8	3 ab	3 b	1.0
50	2 d	2 c	1.0	1 b	0	0.0
60	1 d	0 c	0.0	0 b	0	0.0

^aTotal of 6 replications. In the same column, means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 1% level of probability. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

with similar tillering abilities, IR5 and GH106-76, were sown at 10-day intervals. Seedlings 21 days after sowing

(DS) were transplanted separately at 2 seedlings/pot. Rice plants 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, and 10 days after transplanting (DT)